

SOCIAL, PSYCHOLOGICAL, DIAGNOSTIC AND CORRECTION ASPECTS OF PROVIDING FAMILY STABILITY

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Abstract. *This article presents the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on July 28, 2017 and the role of child rearing in ensuring family stability, important principles of continuing child rearing in the family and social, psychological, diagnostic and corrective aspects, opinions of foreign scientists.*

Keywords: *Family, education, child, principle, socio-spiritual environment, society, parents, disputes.*

In their research, many scientists have conducted a number of scientific researches on the main factors of moral decline in social relations, all kinds of interesting analytical data have been based, but among them, one factor that worries a person, which at first glance seems to be neglected, but which leads to decline and ignorance, is the origin of conflicts in the family. one of the reasons goes back to child education.

Neglect of child rearing in the family was noted as an internal threat in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 28, 2017 “On increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work and raising the field to a new level of development” [1], and the task of effective ideological struggle against this threat was set. Examples can be given from the results of surveys conducted on the basis of “Determining the state of socio-spiritual environment in the society and method of targeted rehabilitation” and “Concept of continuous spiritual education”. In particular, what do you think is causing the parents to raise their children well among the population in this diagnostic work?” to the question, parents in Navoi (60%), Jizzakh (57.4%), Syrdarya (57%), Samarkand (53%), Bukhara (44%) regions and Tashkent city (50%) do not know the methods of education and answered that they do not understand the responsibility of the family, these indicators indicate that parents should seriously consider the issue of paying attention to child education.

Every family is a small society. Peaceful living of the family, good life, elimination of the origin of conflicts in the family in positive ways should be the goals and tasks of each family member. In order for the family to live peacefully, we need to choose the right family education technology. We know that education is a process that takes place from birth to the end of a person's life. Education is the teacher's inculcation of desired qualities in the mind of the student. Education, first of all, begins with the family, so as the thinker scientist Alisher Navoi said, parents should give their child a good name and raise it well, a good name determines the child's future, and a good education prepares the child for life. One of the tried-and-tested methods of raising children in the family is a role model. Grandfather, grandmother, parents, behavior of adults around the child, behavior, behavior, behavior, attitudes towards education as an example have a great

educational value. The basics of mental, moral, aesthetic, labor education are instilled in the child based on the example of the parents.

It is necessary for parents to set an example in front of their children with their intelligence, manners, clothes, determination, hard work, and fairness in family management. Quarrels of parents, negative attitude towards family, society, environment, lying, indecisiveness, sloppiness in dressing, livelihood, lack of love for work quickly affect the child's character.

At this point, N.K.Krupskaya believes that it is possible to achieve success in educating the young generation only when the school, family and community work together. Noting that it is important that all educational forces work in continuity to form the personality of young people, not only some people educate the child, rather, family education and the whole school process educates, street music educates, educational institutions, the surrounding environment, the entire social system educates, events and events in society educate [2].

Here are some of the most important principles of continuous child-rearing in the family:

family upbringing is based on scientific heritage:

family upbringing is based on life experience:

Basics of effective organization of free time in family education:

Ways to organize diligence in family education:

polite upbringing of children in the family:

to create good qualities in the family:

important means of raising family and children honestly, etc.[3]

In some families, all the work of raising children is entrusted to the mother, and the father pays little attention to these important tasks. It is a big mistake to approach the upbringing of the child, and the father's absence from the task of raising his child.

In order to protect children from conflicts in the future, it is necessary to pay attention to the following points in child education:

1. If the parents give the child enough affection and love, his self-confidence will increase and his sorrows and fears will decrease.

2. Children who are often beaten at home and always blamed feel like naughty children who have hurt their parents. They consider themselves to be guilty of even the smallest thing. This feeling causes them to become irritable for no reason, to become disillusioned with their home and family as a disobedient child.

3. If a parent has a calm and patient relationship with their child as much as possible, there is no need to give him extra lessons and reminders. It is already known that dry advice is not useful in raising a child.

4. Being a good parent doesn't take a lot of pretense. In this regard, sincerity is enough. After all, too much love and attention makes a child selfish.

5. When a child does something wrong, it is not appropriate to reprimand him and say, "You never do what you say, when you become a man, you will always cause us worry." Instead of blaming the child, it is best to listen to him patiently until the end of his speech. The reason is that the child's love for his family increases when he sees that his parents are trying to side with him, and it becomes easier for him to admit his wrongdoing. When this is done, the child tells everything openly and makes a promise to himself not to repeat his mistakes again. If the parents behave in the opposite way, the child does not trust his family, does not seek to solve problems

together. A parent who listens to his child and tries to understand him will keep his respect in the eyes of the child.

6. In the case of misunderstanding or disagreement between children, it is wrong to reprimand without knowing which one is wrong. If both are punished, the guilty child's trust in the parents will weaken, and he will start to look at his brother with a grudge. For this reason, if serious situations do not arise, not getting into the middle, disagreements, and creating an opportunity for children to solve conflicts themselves will also help them to grow up as sincere and honest people.

7. A child should believe that he can overcome difficulties, problems, and various disputes from the moment he takes his first step to school. Answer his questions in a way that he understands. The child's failure should not be seen as a disaster. Encourage him, teach him to get up when he stumbles and move forward.

8. It is not appropriate to follow the path of "evil for evil" in raising a child.

9. There is no place for beating in child education. Perhaps it is possible to deter a child from doing bad things by beating him for a certain period of time. But after the impact of the beating is over, the child may repeat the same mistakes again. Frequent use of beatings and other punishments in education causes the child to develop feelings instead of feeling sorry for his mistakes [4]. It can be seen from the above that parents must have certain knowledge and experience in child care and education. If you think we're late for this, you'd be wrong. Let us always strive to correct our mistakes today. Taking the first step is half the battle. Let's not forget that if a family is a thing, then a child is the most beautiful rose of that thing. The smile of this beautiful bud is the greatest happiness for the family.

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